

Fully bio-based wood adhesives from lignin and zein protein

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Abstract

Manufacturing of wood-based panels predominantly relies on formaldehyde-containing adhesives, whose volatile organic compound emissions raise serious concerns about indoor air quality and human health. Although bio-based adhesives derived from proteins, polysaccharides, or lignin have been explored, achieving strong bonding performance while maintaining green, scalable, and practical processability remains challenging. In this study, we present a waterborne wood adhesive in which zein protein is dispersed within a viscous micellar lignin gel. Drawing inspiration from the interactions between proteins and polyphenols, we designed this system to be fully bio-based and free of cross-linkers. When birch veneers were hot-pressed with this adhesive, the resulting three- to five-layer plywood materials showed competitive performance compared with existing bio-based adhesive formulations. Meanwhile, this approach also delivers favorable green metrics, including an Eco-scale score of 94, supported by absence of organic solvents, the minimal number of steps, and the water-borne nature of the formulation. Notably, the adhesive can be debonded in a 70% ethanol-water solution, allowing its recovery and reuse. The combined results indicate the potential of the lignin-protein system as a sustainable alternative to conventional petroleum-based commercial adhesives for indoor use.

Green foundation

This work presents a fully bio-based, waterborne lignin-zein adhesive for plywood applications. Zein protein is dispersed within a lignin gel to form a continuous adhesive network without the need for synthetic cross-linkers or petroleum-derived resins, following green chemistry principles.

This adhesive formulation delivers competitive bonding performance together with favorable green metrics, including a high Eco-scale score, low E-factor and process mass intensity values, supported by its simple preparation, minimal processing steps and high material efficiency. The system exhibits debond-on-demand behavior, allowing bonded wood specimens to be separated in an ethanol/water solution, followed by recovery, reuse and reprocessing of the adhesive.

Future developments may focus on improving water resistance while preserving the debond-on-demand behavior, reusability and fully bio-based nature of the adhesive.

Introduction

Petroleum-based adhesives such as urea-formaldehyde (UF), melamine-formaldehyde (MF), and phenol-formaldehyde (PF) adhesives continue to predominate in wood composites due to their high strength and rapid thermal curing.¹ However, stricter environmental regulations and requirements to reduce formaldehyde emissions continue to drive demand for wood composites that meet environmental standards.^{2,3} In Europe, particularly in Sweden, wood-based panels are classified according to their emissions limit (e.g., E1 \leq 0.124 mg/m³), reflecting strict indoor air quality standards.⁴ There is thus a need for new bio-based adhesive formulations that simultaneously ensure low emission levels, sufficient adhesive strength, and compatibility with industrial applications.

To replace traditional petrochemical adhesives, a wide range of bio-based materials has been explored, including polysaccharides such as starch and hemicellulose, tannins, lignins and plant-derived proteins.⁵⁻¹¹ Natural biomacromolecules such as proteins and lignins are promising candidates for developing formaldehyde-free adhesives, considering their green and renewable source, high bonding strength, and potential biodegradability.^{12,13} Among readily available renewable biomass feedstocks, lignin has attracted increasing interest as an adhesive component, owing in part to its natural role as a binder in woody plant tissues. Because of its complex, mostly aromatic macromolecular structure, lignin can improve the mechanical properties of polymer matrices, making them more heat-resistant, rigid, and resistant to UV radiation.^{14,15} To overcome the poor and often incomplete solubility in water, aqueous dispersions of colloidal lignin particles can be prepared and used in a wide range of materials, including hair conditioners and bio-based adhesives.¹⁶ Lignin extracted in the presence of formaldehyde can be used

as wood adhesives, demonstrating competitive performance in plywood applications.¹⁷ These studies highlight lignin as a promising component in the development of more environmentally friendly, sustainable adhesive systems that can fully replace petroleum-based analogues.

In recent years, increasing interest has been directed toward lignin-protein systems, and their combination governed by intermolecular interactions between functional groups.¹⁸ Lignin can interact with amino acid residues of proteins through hydrogen bonds, van der Waals forces, π - π stacking, and cation- π interactions, forming a stable three-dimensional network.^{19,20} Despite the properties described above, the use of lignin-protein systems in fully bio-based adhesives remains limited. At the formulation level, lignin and proteins present significant physicochemical challenges, as technical lignins are poorly water-soluble and structurally heterogeneous, while proteins are sensitive to pH and processing conditions, which affect their conformation and stability.²¹ As a result, blending often leads to heterogeneous systems or phase separation rather than a continuous network. Consequently, most of the described lignin-protein adhesive systems rely on chemical modification or external crosslinking agents to achieve strong adhesion.^{22,23} Therefore, the development of a simple, water-based adhesive system without crosslinking agents remains challenging and a relatively unexplored area.

Among the available technical proteins, zein, a hydrophobic protein resulting from corn milling, has lately attracted interest. The low content of essential amino acids (in particular, lysine and tryptophan) makes zein an excellent bio-based candidate for developing sustainable materials since does not compete with human feeding.^{24,25} Zein is used as a film former, a matrix for encapsulating bioactive substances, and as a basis for biodegradable packaging materials and adhesive systems.^{26,27} However, despite these advantages, zein's pronounced hydrophobicity hinders the formation of stable, homogeneous aqueous mixtures limiting their use in a fully water-based adhesive formulations. This work presents a facile method for preparing a waterborne, fully bio-based adhesive that does not contain formaldehyde or organic solvents. The adhesive is prepared by mixing lignin gel with zein, followed by adjusting the water content to the required solid matter content.²⁸ The resulting composition demonstrates strong adhesion to wood and allows the production of three- and five-layer plywood under hot-pressing conditions. In addition to bonding performance, the system was evaluated for controlled debonding and adhesive reuse. In this work, reuse refers to separation of bonded wood components in a 70% ethanol/water (w/w) solution under mild heating, followed by partial extraction, reconstitution and reuse of the adhesive material. This concept is relevant for end-of-life disassembly of indoor wood-based products and temporary wooden constructions, where controlled debonding may enable partial recovery and reuse of the adhesive material. It may also be useful in manufacturing scenarios where incorrectly bonded parts need to be debonded and the adhesive material recovered. Thus, the developed system represents a waterborne, bio-based adhesive platform with strong dry bonding performance and suitable for debonding-on-demand concept usage.

Results and discussions

Waterborne lignin-zein adhesive formulation and curing behavior

The goal of this work is to develop a bio-based adhesive aligned with the principles of green chemistry, avoiding the use of organic solvents or external crosslinking agents.²⁹ The formulation is based on a lignin gel formed through dissolution of poorly water-soluble softwood kraft lignin under alkali conditions with sodium lignosulfonates, followed by pH neutralization.²⁸ During the neutralization step, lignin self-organization led to the formation of a stable colloidal micellar gel. This enables the production of the lignin gel without any organic solvents or energy-intensive evaporation steps, which is a key advantage of this environmentally friendly method. To prepare adhesives, freshly made lignin gel was mixed with zein at high shear rates until a homogeneous dispersion was obtained (Fig. 1). Water was added to adjust the formulation to 42 wt% solid content, selected to balance adhesive loading, rheological properties and processing stability during veneer application and hot pressing.

To evaluate adhesive processability, the apparent viscosity of the lignin gel and lignin-zein formulations was measured as a function of shear rate (Fig. S1). The lignin gel showed shear-thinning behavior, with apparent viscosity decreasing as the shear rate increased. This behavior was retained after zein addition, indicating that the lignin-zein formulations retained suitable for spreading despite the incorporation of water-insoluble zein. The apparent viscosity varied with the lignin/zein ratio and the formulation containing 30% lignin showed the highest viscosity at low shear rates. However, the lignin-zein adhesives remained spreadable and could be applied onto wood veneers. This retained spreadability is important for adhesive processing, as the material becomes easier to distribute under shear during application. Thus, the lignin gel acts as a water-based dispersing matrix that enables zein incorporation without

While comparing the tensile stress at a fixed curing time, it was found that an increase in protein content led to greater strength. It is noteworthy to mention that in the case of adhesive formulation with higher protein content, the nature of the break appears in the form of wood failure (Fig. 2c), confirming the formation of a strong interface and adhesive network in the joint. When the curing time was increased to 15 minutes, a slight decrease in strength appeared. This could be explained by over-drying of the adhesive joint and the formation of micro-cracks, as well as by over-compaction associated with joint brittleness. From this point of view, 5 minutes was selected as an optimum curing time for the subsequent samples. This duration provides maximum mechanical properties with minimum heat exposure, processing time, and energy consumption, resulting in short, efficient curing cycles in line with hot-pressing at an industrial scale. To gain insights into structural changes, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to analyse individual components that compose the adhesive, zein and lignin gel, adhesive itself

Fig. 2. Multifaceted characterization of lignin-protein adhesives: a) Optimization of the hot-pressing conditions for the adhesive (15 minutes curing at a temperature range from 60 °C to 150 °C). Different letters over the bars indicate significant differences between groups according to Tukey's post-hoc test following one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$). Groups sharing the same letter are not significantly different. b) Adhesive strength kinetics for three different formulations (30%, 50%, 70% lignin content) at 150 °C from 1 to 15 minutes c) A photograph showing wood failure after tensile strength testing of sample (10 minutes curing, 50% lignin adhesive formulation). d) FTIR spectra for zein protein, lignin gel, adhesive before and after curing e) TGA analysis of zein and lignin gel samples f) TGA analysis of different adhesive formulations

before and after hot-pressing (Fig. 2d). The zein protein spectrum shows characteristic protein absorption bands. The broad band observed at 3300 - 3400 cm⁻¹ corresponds to overlapping O-H and N-H stretching vibrations associated with hydroxyl groups and amide functional groups linked by hydrogen bonds. The bands at 1650 cm⁻¹ and 1540 cm⁻¹ correspond to amide I (C=O stretching) and amide II (N-H bending and C-N stretching) vibrations, respectively, which are typical features of the secondary protein structure.³⁰ Additional bands in the 1450 - 1400 cm⁻¹ and 1230 - 1050 cm⁻¹ correspond to C-H bending and C-N/C-O stretching of protein backbone, respectively. The lignin gel exhibits characteristic bands of aromatic structures. A broad peak at 3400 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the stretching vibrations of phenolic and aliphatic O-H. The band in the 1200 - 1000 cm⁻¹ region refers to C-O stretching vibrations associated with phenolic groups.³¹ The presence of amide I and amide II bands, together with aromatic lignin bands, confirms that both lignin and protein phases are preserved in the adhesive composition. After hot pressing at 150 °C, slight changes were observed, with the general positions of the bands remaining largely unchanged. This indicates that no new covalent chemical bonds were formed during the curing process. However, a broadening of the O-H/N-H band at 3300 - 3400 cm⁻¹ suggests changes in hydrogen bonding interactions within the lignin-zein adhesive matrix. These observations support a curing process mainly associated with non-covalent interactions between lignin and zein, including hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions between lignin aromatic domains and non-polar regions of the protein, and van der Waals interactions.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed under nitrogen atmosphere to evaluate the thermal degradation of pure zein and a lignin gel (Fig. 2e). All samples were pre-dried to minimize the influence of residual moisture. Pure zein demonstrated a sharp initial decomposition step between 280 - 380 °C, corresponding to the protein degradation range.³² In contrast, lignin gel displayed a slower degradation over an applied temperature range, consistent with its complex aromatic structure and its well-known char-forming ability under inert conditions.³³ Lignin-zein adhesive demonstrates intermediate thermal behaviour with an identical decomposition region as for pure zein, but with a less sharp mass loss profile, and can be compared with adhesive formulations containing varying amounts of lignin (Fig. 2f). All samples showed a similar thermogravimetric behaviour with a main decomposition step at a temperature range from 250 °C to 350 °C.³⁴ As expected, an increase in lignin content led to a higher residual mass due to its char formation ability. Notably, no significant weight loss was observed near 150 °C, and the onset of the major decomposition step occurred at temperatures above 250 °C. This demonstrates that the adhesive's hot-press curing occurred well below its thermal decomposition range.

Fig. 3. Morphological and elemental characterization of the adhesive: a) SEM images of adhesive surface (50% lignin, 150 °C, 15 min) b) EDS analysis of the cured adhesive surface c) Optical microscopy images of adhesive (50% lignin) before and after curing (5 min, 150 °C).

However, the absence of the major mass loss at 150 °C indicates stability against thermal decomposition, but does not exclude conformational rearrangement, denaturation or aggregation of zein during hot pressing. Heat-induced structural changes in zein have been reported previously, including changes in intermolecular interactions, protein configuration and aggregate morphology after thermal treatment.³⁵ In the present adhesive, zein is not present as an

isolated protein phase but is incorporated into a lignin-rich water-based matrix, which acts as a dispersing medium under aqueous conditions. Therefore, any thermally induced zein restructuring would occur in the presence of lignin, where hydrogen bonding and restricted protein mobility may influence the final morphology of the cured adhesive. Such thermally induced restructuring may contribute to consolidation of the lignin-zein adhesive matrix during curing. The morphology of the cured lignin-zein adhesive surface hot-pressed on a wood veneer (50% lignin, 150 °C, 15 min) was analysed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and the resulting images at different magnifications are shown in (Fig. 3a). SEM images reveal a continuous surface with no visible phase separation or macroscopic cracks/ruptures. This visual observation indicates effective densification of the adhesive layer under the chosen curing conditions. To evaluate the distribution of elements across the adhesive surface, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping was used (Fig. 3b). Dominant carbon (C) and oxygen (O) signals, corresponding to the organic nature of both zein and lignin, were observed across the whole

Fig. 4. Engineering assessment for plywood and particleboard: a) Plywood specimen with notches for mechanical testing according to EN-314 standard protocol b) Tensile strength of three layers plywood hot pressed at 150°C for 5 minutes, dashed line indicates the benchmark for dry plywood bonding c) A photograph showing wood failure after tensile strength testing of three-layer plywood samples (50% adhesive formulation) d) Plywood orientation e) Images of three- and five-layers plywood f) Particleboard prepared from sawdust g) Modulus of rupture (MOR) of sawdust-based particleboards. Different letters over the bars in panels b) and g) indicate significant differences between groups according to Tukey’s post-hoc test following one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$). Groups sharing the same letter are not significantly different.

scanned region. The nitrogen (N) signal, derived mainly from the protein fraction, was evenly distributed across the adhesive surface, indicating uniform incorporation of protein into the adhesive matrix. Further, sodium (Na) and sulfur (S), associated with salts in the lignin gel, were distributed across the sample. The absence of clear element-rich domains suggests that the cured adhesive surface remained uniform at the observed scale.

Optical microscopy was used to visualize the adhesive morphology in water before and after curing (Fig. 3c). The non-cured adhesive exhibits a dispersed microstructure, characterized by agglomerates of varying sizes distributed

throughout the phase. The presence of large agglomerates is attributed to the salts in the lignin gel formulation, while some larger aggregates likely originated from the undissolved protein in the aqueous mixture. After curing at 150 °C, the morphology became more homogeneous, with a greater number of smaller particles and fewer large aggregates. This observation indicates thermally driven reorganization of the adhesive network, as evidenced by the mechanical properties observed in subsequent tensile strength tests.

Mechanical performance of plywood and sawdust-based boards

To evaluate the adhesive's characteristics in a more practical context, plywood samples were prepared using optimized adhesive conditions. For the preparation of three-layer plywood birch veneers, 1.5 mm-thick were used. The moisture content of the veneers before gluing was 8%. The adhesive was applied with a dry spread rate (83 g/m²)

Fig. 5. Microstructure analysis of the plywood adhesive joint (30% lignin adhesive formulation, 150 °C, 5 min): **a)** SEM image of the wood-adhesive interface with EDS mapping, **b)** Optical microscopy images of a microtome-cut plywood cross-section; the right image is color-coded for visual clarity.

over one side and evenly distributed by spatula. A three-layer plywood was assembled, with the middle veneer layer oriented with the fibers along the axis and the outer layers placed perpendicular, thereby achieving classic cross-layering to minimize warping and anisotropy (Fig. 4d). After hot pressing at 150 °C under 1 MPa for 5 minutes, the samples were cooled and trimmed. The specimens for measuring strength were cut according to the EN-314-1 standard.³⁶ Each specimen was 100×25 mm, with a notch on each side that intersected the entire first layer and half of the middle layer (Fig. 4a). The same was done on the other side, ensuring that the distance between the clamps during measurement was more than 50 mm. Before tensile measurement, each sample was conditioned for 24 hours at 23°C and 50% relative humidity (RH). The measurements were performed under dry conditions, without water immersion pretreatment.

To clarify the role of the individual components, single-component control formulations were evaluated under the same water conditions. The lignin gel alone formed a spreadable paste but did not form a stable bonded joint after hot pressing. The zein only control, in contrast, could not be processed into a homogeneous water-based adhesive paste because of its limited solubility and instead formed aggregated, poorly spreadable material (Fig. S2).

The average tensile shear strengths of the samples were 2.8 ± 0.5 MPa, 2.1 ± 0.6 MPa and 2.2 ± 0.3 MPa for the adhesive formulations containing 30%, 50% and 70% lignin, respectively (Fig. 4b and Fig. S3). For each measurement six samples been tested (n=6). One-way ANOVA showed a significant overall effect of adhesive

formulation on bonding strength ($p = 0.028$). Tukey post-hoc analysis showed that the 30% lignin formulation was significantly higher than the 50% lignin formulation ($p = 0.038$), while the other pairwise comparisons did not reach statistical significance at $p < 0.05$. The tensile strength measurements were accompanied by wood failure (Fig. 4c), in accordance with the adhesive's surface contribution from zein and the cohesive role of lignin gel. The average shear strength values significantly exceed 1.0 MPa, which is commonly used as a reference threshold in plywood bonding assessments. The applicability of the adhesive for the preparation of multilayer plywood was further demonstrated by preparing five-layer plywood with a similar cross-layering orientation (each neighbouring layer is perpendicular to the previous one)(Fig. 4e). The same pressing conditions were used as for the three-layer plywood manufacturing.

To demonstrate the adhesive's versatility beyond plywood, sawdust-based particleboards were prepared and quantitatively characterized (Fig. 4f). The boards were formed in a 160×160×4.3 mm mold. The same lignin-zein adhesive formulations used for plywood bonding were used for sawdust-based particleboard preparation. The stock adhesive formulation had a solids content of 42 wt% and was diluted with water before mixing with sawdust to improve adhesive distribution throughout the sawdust particle network. For each board, 89 g of sawdust was mixed with dry adhesive solids, corresponding to an adhesive loading of approximately 7.2 wt% based on dry sawdust.

Fig. 6. Reusing of lignin-protein adhesives: a) Schematic illustration of reusing lignin-protein adhesives b) Tensile strength measurements for glued wood samples after first and second reusing (150 °C, 5 minutes hot-press curing, 30% lignin) c) TGA analysis of the reused adhesive.

The resulting water-diluted adhesive formulation had a solids content of 8 wt%. After forming, the boards were hot-pressed at 150 °C under 1 MPa for 5 min, using the same pressing conditions as for the plywood materials. Water absorption and thickness swelling were measured after 2, 6, 12 and 24 h immersion in water. After 24 h immersion, the water absorption values were $153.9 \pm 15.8\%$, $165.2 \pm 22.0\%$ and $151.9 \pm 12.9\%$, while the thickness swelling values were $144.2 \pm 7.7\%$, $121.8 \pm 15.0\%$ and $97.9 \pm 7.5\%$ for the adhesive formulations containing 70%, 50% and 30% lignin, respectively (Table S1). Three-point bending tests were performed to evaluate the mechanical performance of the pressed boards. The modulus of rupture (MOR) values were 21.5 ± 9.9 MPa, 29.9 ± 6.9 MPa and 37.6 ± 6.8 MPa for the adhesive formulations containing 70%, 50% and 30% lignin respectively (Fig. 4g). These results demonstrate effective bonding of sawdust particles by the lignin-zein adhesive. Among the tested compositions, the 30% lignin formulation provided the best overall particleboard performance, combining the highest flexural strength with the lowest thickness swelling at all measured time points and the comparable water absorption.

Interfacial bond-line morphology and adhesive distribution

To better understand the structure of the adhesive layer and its interactions with wood, optical and SEM images of plywood cross-sections were captured (Fig. S4). The cross-section of three-layer plywood, pressed at 150 °C under 1 MPa for 5 minutes, was characterized by SEM equipped with EDS mapping (Fig. 5a). For both SEM and EDS mapping, an accelerating voltage of 15 kV was used. The cross-sectional images showed the adhesive line as a continuous, dense layer between neighbouring wood veneer layers, without visible microcracks and with uniform distribution along the entire length of the adhesive joint. This suggests that water evaporation during hot-pressing did not disrupt the adhesive layer. Although the formulation is water-based, the adhesive is a viscous lignin-zein paste, which helps maintain the adhesive components at the interface during heating. As water is gradually removed, the lignin-zein components become concentrated between the veneer layers, contributing to densification of the bond line. EDS mapping reveals the chemical structure of the narrow adhesive line between three layers of veneer, where S signals indicating the presence of lignosulfonates and Na signals originating from the corresponding salts in lignin gel. Outside the joint, on the wood surface, the intensities of S and Na drop to background levels, consistent with their absence in the wood. The N signal, an identifier of zein protein due to its amino groups, was more widely distributed not only in the adhesive layer but also in the wood parts on both sides of the adhesive seam. This could be since possible contribution from nitrogen containing species in technical lignin and residual nitrogen-containing components naturally present in wood veneer.³⁷ Peaks from C and O dominated the entire surface of the specimen, without clear localization. These observations are consistent with the adhesive EDS analysis in (Fig. 3b), confirming a homogeneous distribution of lignin and zein components within the adhesive formulation, without the formation of distinct segregated domains (Fig. S5-6).

Optical microscopy was used to analyse cross-sections of plywood and visualize the bonding morphology (Fig. 5b). 20 µm thick sections were prepared with a microtome perpendicular to the adhesive interface. The optical images show an area with two glued veneers separated by a clear adhesive layer in the middle. As seen in a color-coded optical image, the lignin-zein-based adhesive formed a continuous bonding line at the interface, clearly distinguishable from the surrounding wood tissue. Near the interface, local penetration of the adhesive into the surface vessels and lumens was observed, although no overpenetration into the main wood structure was detected. The wood remains unchanged, with no large breaks or gaps, indicating a uniform distribution of the adhesive layer at this scale. Therefore, the observed rigid adhesive matrix, free of cracks or defects and partially penetrating the wood's surface layer, provides plywood with high strength and is consistent with the observed wood failure pattern.

Debonding, adhesive recovery and sustainability assessment

The increasing use of wood materials requires not only strong adhesive performance but also the ability to debond bonded components and recover the adhesive for reuse, enabling its return to the production cycle with minimal loss.⁴⁰ Consequently, increasing attention is being focused on the development of debonding-on-demand adhesives that enable controlled disassembly upon exposure of external triggers as solvents, heat or pH changes.⁴¹⁻⁴³ As shown in (Fig. 6a), a recovery and reuse method for the lignin-protein adhesives was developed and tested. Single-lap specimens bonded by hot pressing at 150 °C for 5 minutes were first immersed in 70% ethanol/water solution at 60 °C for 30 minutes (Step 2). A colour change occurred in the solution after a few minutes, indicating extraction of adhesive components from the bonded joint. The resulting solution was filtered to separate insoluble wood-derived residues and then the resulting filtered solution was slowly evaporated at 40 °C (Step 3). In Step 4, the adhesive reconstitution was done by adding water to adjust the solids working content to 42%. In the final step, the reused adhesive was used to bond new single-lap wooden joints using the same pressing format, with a glued section of 272 mm² area. The recovery yield of adhesive was calculated from the dry mass of recovered adhesive relative to the dry mass of adhesive initially used in the bonded joints. The recovery yields were 62.3% after the first recovery cycle and 70.1% after the second recovery cycle. These yields are consistent with the mild extraction conditions, which were selected to enable debonding and recovery without harsh chemical treatment or severe damage to the wood substrate. Under these conditions, part of the adhesive is expected to remain inside surface pores or attached to the wood cells after hot pressing. Importantly,

despite the partial material recovery, the recovered adhesive retained functional bonding ability. The strength of glued specimens was evaluated by the maximum breaking force measured on the Instron Universal. For the original sample, before reusing, the maximum breaking force reached 1101 N (4.0 MPa shear strength). After the first and second reusing cycles, the maximum breaking force dropped to 858 N (3.1 MPa) and 705 N (2.6 MPa), respectively (Fig. 6b and Fig. S7). The gradual decrease in bond strength after each reusing cycle could be explained by several factors. During initial pressing, the adhesive partially penetrated the wood's surface pores and adhered to the walls. Therefore, this prevented its full recovery during our mild ethanol extraction method. Another factor could be that, despite filtration, a small fraction of soluble wood extract passed the

Table 1. Comparison of hazard pictograms and solvents used in lignin-based adhesives.

Components	Hazard pictograms	Solvent system	Ref
Lignin – glyoxal		Water	3
Uncondensed lignins		Organic solvents	17
Oxidized alkali lignin – soy protein		DMF, water	22
Demethylated lignin – soy protein		DMF, water	23
Lignin – glycerol diglycidyl ether		Water	38
Epoxidized lignin		Organic solvents	39
Lignin – zein protein	-	Water	This work

recovery stage and ended up in the dry recovered adhesive, reducing both the adhesive's spreadability within the pores and its mechanical strength. In addition, possible irreversible thermal restructuring of zein during repeated hot-pressed cycles may also contribute to the decrease in bonding strength. As discussed above, zein may undergo conformational rearrangement, denaturation and aggregation at the hot-pressing temperature. While such heat-induced restructuring may contribute to adhesive consolidation during curing, it may also reduce the ability of the recovered adhesive to fully redisperse and reform the same adhesive matrix in subsequent reuse cycles.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed to evaluate the thermal stability of the adhesives after each recycling step, compared with the original adhesive formulation containing 30% lignin (Fig. 6c). All samples exhibit similar thermogravimetric behaviour, with a main decomposition step in the temperature range of 250-350 °C. The first and second reused samples showed nearly overlapping thermograms, indicating that the mild recovery procedure did not cause substantial changes in the thermal degradation profile of the adhesive. These results demonstrate the possibility of disassembling the adhesive joint and further functional reuse without significant degradation, which is essential for the huge sector of temporary wooden constructions.

Despite significant progress in developing biobased wood adhesives, the challenge of finding environmentally sustainable formulations that can compete with traditional petrochemical alternatives remains a major issue. In recent years, a variety of adhesives based on lignin, tannin, proteins, and other environmentally friendly materials have been reported.⁴⁴ To position our work within this context, Table 1 summarizes representative lignin-based adhesive systems. As highlighted, formulations that are truly free of both organic solvents and crosslinking agents remain relatively rare. In this regard, the adhesive developed in this work is fully water-based, avoiding the use of organic solvents and crosslinking agents classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic, or toxic to reproduction (CMR). This simple formulation strategy leads to high green performance metrics.

Green metrics

The incorporation of lignin as a renewable component of materials is a recognized green strategy, highlighting the potential of lignin-containing binders to replace petrochemical systems.⁸ In this work, zein was dispersed in an aqueous lignin gel without use of organic solvents or external crosslinking agents. The environmental profile of the adhesive preparation was evaluated using E-factor, process mass intensity (PMI), process mass productivity (PMP) and Eco-scale.⁴⁵ The E-factor is defined as the mass of waste generated per mass of product, while PMI is defined as the total mass of input materials required to obtain one unit mass of product. In this work, both metrics were calculated using dry adhesive solids as the product basis, since water acts as the processing medium and is removed during hot pressing. For the adhesive formulation containing 50% lignin, the E-factor was 1.34 and the PMI was 2.34 (Table S2). A PMI of 2.34 means that 2.34 kg of total input material is required to obtain 1 kg of dry adhesive solids. PMP expresses the same mass-efficiency relationship in percentage form and was calculated as the inverse of PMI: $PMP = 1/PMI \times 100\%$. Thus, the PMI value of 2.34 corresponds to a PMP of 42.6%. Since the adhesive is prepared as a waterborne formulation, the non-product mass in these calculations is associated with water removal during hot pressing rather than hazardous solvents. Eco-scale was used as a complementary penalty-based assessment of the adhesive preparation (Table S3). The score was calculated by starting from an ideal value of 100 and subtracting penalty points for yield, reagent cost, safety, temperature/time or technical setup. In this process, no penalty was assigned for safety or workup/purification, because the formulation uses low-hazard bio-based components and water as the processing medium. A penalty of 3 points was assigned for the technical setup because hot pressing requires pressure equipment and an additional penalty of 3 points was assigned for temperature/time requirements, accounting for overnight stirring during lignin gel preparation. Therefore, the total penalty was 6 points, giving an Eco-scale score of 94. Together, these values indicate a favourable process profile for the lignin-zein adhesives preparation, combining reasonable material efficiency with a waterborne, solvent-free formulation and a high Eco-scale score.

Fig. 7. Comparison of dry bonding strength to bio-based content for three-layer plywood.^{3,17,46-60} The values used in this graph can be found (Table S4).

As shown in (Fig.7), the strength of fully bio-based adhesives is generally limited, whereas higher performance is often associated with chemical modification or partial substitution with non-based components. This work provides competitive bond strength with 100% bio-based content in the absence of external cross-linking agents. It is particularly impressive as it is achieved in fully water-based formulation, indicating the potential to overcome the traditional limitations of bio-based adhesive systems and paving the way for the development of environmentally sustainable and highly effective alternatives for wood bonding.

Conclusions

In this work, we developed a waterborne bio-based adhesive based on zein protein and lignin gel, without use of formaldehyde, organic solvents or external crosslinking agents. The adhesive system was systematically investigated in terms of processability, dry bonding performance, thermal behaviour, particleboard applicability, green metrics and reusability. Single-component control experiments further showed that the combined lignin-zein formulation provide a better balance of water-based processability and bonding performance than either component alone. The adhesive demonstrated strong dry bonding performance in plywood and the formulation containing 30% lignin giving the highest average tensile shear strength among the tested compositions. Microscopy and EDS analysis revealed the formation of a continuous adhesive line at the wood interface without visible macroscopic defects or distinct segregated domains. Beyond plywood, the adhesive was also applied to sawdust-based particleboards, where water absorption, thickness swelling and three-point bending measurements showed composition-dependent performance. Among the tested particleboards formulations, the 30% lignin adhesive showed the best overall performance, combining the highest flexural strength with the lowest thickness swelling. The adhesive demonstrated potential for controlled debonding and reuse by extracting the adhesive material with a 70% ethanol/water solution under mild conditions, followed by re-processing. Thermal analysis of the recycled adhesive indicated that the main thermal characteristics were retained after reusing cycles, indicating that the adhesive system's structure was preserved. Overall, the results show that lignin and protein-based compositions can form effective bio-adhesives without the need for chemical cross-linking agents. The combination of high adhesive strength, practical processability, reusability and favourable green metrics highlights the potential of lignin-protein-based systems as an alternative to traditional synthetic wood adhesives for indoor applications.

Experimental

Materials and methods

Sodium lignosulfonate (DS10, Domsjö, Sweden), softwood kraft lignin (SKL, BioPiva 100, UPM, Finland), zein (22-24 kDa, Sigma Aldrich), sulfuric acid (VWR, Sweden), sodium hydroxide (VWR, Sweden), wood veneers (1.5 mm thickness, Koskisen, Finland), wood specimens (1.5 mm thickness, Flying Tiger, Sweden), wood chips (Vitakraft, Bauhaus, Sweden). Detailed characterization data for the lignin components are provided in Table S5.

Protein structure visualization

The zein protein structure shown in Fig.1 was obtained from the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database and visualized using Open-Source PyMOL (The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 4.6, Schrödinger, LLC).^{61,62} The structure is used for schematic visualization of the zein component in adhesive formulation.

Colloidal lignin gel preparation

The colloidal lignin gel was prepared according to our earlier work.²⁸ Briefly, sodium lignosulfonate (510 g, dry) and softwood kraft lignin (102 g, dry) were dissolved in a 5:1 ratio in 746 mL of 2 M sodium hydroxide solution, and the mixture was left stirred overnight. Then, 144 mL of water was added at pH ~ 13.5. Finally, 175 mL of 2 M sulfuric acid solution was added dropwise to obtain a lignin gel with a pH of ~ 5.6. The obtained lignin gel solids content was ~ 41%.

Adhesive preparation

Different protein–lignin adhesives were prepared with protein contents of 30%, 50%, and 70%. The 1:1 ratio lignin-protein adhesive was prepared using 26.3 g of lignin gel dispersed in water (12.7 g), followed by the addition of 12.3 g zein to the colloidal solution. The mixture was homogenized by IKA T-25

Ultra-Turrax (IKA, Germany) for 3 minutes at 15000 rpm. Prepared adhesives were stored at room temperature. The obtained adhesive solids content was ~ 42%.

Bonding strength sample preparation

50 mg of adhesive was applied to 272 square mm² (dry ~ 76 g/m²) on each wood specimens and cured from 1 to 15 minutes using Fontijne LabTop Hot Press at 150 °C under 1 MPa pressure. All the samples were conditioned for 24 hours in a conditioning room (23.1 °C, 50 % RH) after pressing.

Plywood preparation

To prepare three-layer plywood, three layers of veneers (100 × 100 × 1 mm) were glued, adding 1.8 g of adhesive per layer (dry ~ 76 g/m²) with cross-layer orientation; each veneer grain is perpendicular to its neighbouring layer. Glued veneers were cured in Hot Press (Fontijne LabTop) at 150 °C for 5 minutes. All the samples were conditioned for 24 hours (23.1 °C, 50% RH) before tensile strength measurements.

Sawdust-based particleboard preparation

For particleboard preparation, the same stock lignin-zein adhesive formulation used for plywood gluing was diluted with water before mixing with sawdust. For each board, 89 g of sawdust was combined with 6.4 g of dry adhesive solids, giving a dry adhesive loading of 7.2 wt% based on sawdust. After dilution, the adhesive formulation used for sawdust mixing had 8 wt% solid content. The diluted adhesive was added gradually to the sawdust under intensive mixing until the particles were evenly moistened. The mixture was placed into a 160 × 160 × 4.3 mm mold and hot-pressed using a Fontijne LabTop Hot Press at 150 °C under 1 MPa for 5 minutes. The obtained boards were conditioned for 24 h at 23.1 °C and 50% RH before testing.

Green metrics calculation

Green metrics were calculated for the adhesive formulations, following green chemistry metric definitions.⁴⁵ The E-factor, process mass intensity (PMI), process mass productivity (PMP) and Eco-scale were calculated as follows:

E-factor = mass of waste / mass of product; PMI = total mass used in process / mass of product; PMP (%) = (1/PMI) × 100; Eco-scale = 100 – total penalty points. Waste refers to the non-product material generated under the selected calculation boundary. For the Eco-scale assessment, penalty points were assigned based on yield, reagent cost, safety, technical setup, temperature/time and workup/purification.

Characterization methods

Rheological measurements

Rheological measurements were performed using a NETZSCH Kinexus rheometer equipped with a CP4/40 geometry at room temperature. The apparent viscosity of the lignin gel and lignin-zein adhesive formulations was measured as a function of shear rate.

Mechanical test

Mechanical strength measurements were performed by using an Instron 5960 series tensile tester (Instron, USA) equipped with a 10 kN load cell and connected to Bluehill software. The test was performed with a pulling speed of 2 kN/min. The tensile shear strength was calculated as the maximum force divided by the bonded area. The flexural strength of particleboard specimens was measured by three-point bending using an Instron universal testing machine equipped with 1 kN load cell. Rectangular specimens were cut from the pressed boards (160×20×4.3 mm) and the actual width and thickness of each specimen were measured before testing. The support span was set to 80 mm and

the crosshead speed was 2 mm min⁻¹. The modulus of rupture (MOR), was calculated as $MOR = 3F_{max}L / 2bd^2$, where F is the maximum force, L is the support span, b is the specimen width and d is the specimen thickness.

Water absorption and thickness swelling

Water absorption and thickness swelling of particleboards were measured after immersion in water for 2, 6, 12 and 24 h. Specimens dimensions of 50 × 50 × 4.3 mm were used for the measurements. Before immersion, the initial mass and thickness of each specimen were measured. After each immersion time, the specimens were removed from water, gently wiped to remove surface water, weighed and measured for thickness. Thickness was measured at five point and the average value was used for calculation. For each adhesive formulation, three specimens were tested (n = 3). Water absorption and thickness swelling were calculated as follows: WA (%) = $((m_t - m_0) / m_0) \times 100$, TS (%) = $((t_t - t_0) / t_0) \times 100$, where m₀ and t₀ are the initial mass and thickness, and m_t and t_t are the mass and thickness after immersion time.

Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy

Fourier transform infrared spectra were recorded by using a Varian 610-IR FTIR Spectrometer in attenuated total reflection (ATR) mode in the range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ over 32 scans.

Optical microscopy analysis

Optical images were captured using a Nikon ECLIPSE Ti2 inverted microscope. Analysis of the adhesive before and after heat treatment was performed on 1.0wt% diluted samples on the microscopy slides using 4× to 10× objective lenses. To evaluate adhesive penetration into the wood's pores, cross-sections of plywood samples were prepared using a microtome to yield 20 μm-thick sections. The obtained images were colour-enhanced by NIS-Elements software to improve visualization of the adhesive bond.

Scanning electron microscopy

The surface morphology of the adhesive surface was studied by using JEOL JSM-IT800 scanning electron microscope equipped with an EDS detector at an accelerating voltage of 10-15 kV. Cross-sectional images of the plywood sample were captured by a Hitachi TM-3000 scanning electron microscope equipped with a Bruker Quantax 70 EDS system at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV for EDS mapping

Thermal gravimetry analysis

To evaluate thermal stability, thermogravimetric analysis was performed using a PerkinElmer TGA 7 instrument. Samples were heated from 25 °C to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in a nitrogen atmosphere at a flow rate of 20 ml min⁻¹.

Author contributions

R.G. and M.H.S. conceived the idea and designed the experiments. I.P. and M.H.S. supervised the project. R.G., F.W., and M.M. performed the experiments. F.W., M.M., A.J.H., I.P., and M.H.S provided constructive suggestions. R.G., F.W., M.M., A.J.H., I.P. and M.H.S. contributed to data preparation, analysis and manuscript drafting with input from all authors. M.H.S. provided resources for this study. All authors discussed and revised the paper.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

Data availability

All the data supporting this article have been included in the main text and supplementary information (SI). Supplementary information is available.

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References

- 1 I. Calvez, R. Garcia, A. Koubaa, V. Landry and A. Cloutier, *Curr. For. Rep.*, 2024, **10**, 386–400.
- 2 M. H. Hussin, N. H. Abd Latif, T. S. Hamidon, N. N. Idris, R. Hashim, J. N. Appaturi, N. Brosse, I. Ziegler-Devin, L. Chrusiel, W. Fatriasari, F. A. Syamani, A. H. Iswanto, L. S. Hua, S. S. A. O. Al Edrus, W. C. Lum, P. Antov, V. Savov, M. A. Rahandi Lubis, L. Kristak, R. Reh and J. Sedliačik, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, 2022, **21**, 3909–3946.
- 3 M. Siahkamari, S. Emmanuel, D. B. Hodge and M. Nejad, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2022, **10**, 3430–3441.
- 4 Formaldehyde in wood-based boards, <https://www.kemi.se/en/rules-and-regulations/rules-applicable-in-sweden-only/certain-swedish-restrictions-and-bans/formaldehyde-in-wood-based-boards>, (accessed March 13, 2026).
- 5 M. I. Maulana, M. A. R. Lubis, F. Febrianto, L. S. Hua, A. H. Iswanto, P. Antov, L. Kristak, E. Mardawati, R. K. Sari, L. H. Zaini, W. Hidayat, V. L. Giudice and L. Todaro, *Forests*, DOI:10.3390/f13101614.
- 6 T. Todorovic, E. Malmström and L. Fogelström, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2022, **10**, 15372–15379.
- 7 P. V. Dhawale, S. K. Vineeth, R. V. Gadhave, J. F. M. J. M. Vijay Supekar, V. Kumar Thakur and P. Raghavan, *Materials Advances*, 2022, **3**, 3365–3388.
- 8 J. Paez and P. Fatehi, *Green Chemistry*, 2025, **27**, 12499–12537.
- 9 W. Tian, X. Wang, Y. Ye, W. Wu, Y. Wang, S. Jiang, J. Wang and X. Han, *Green Chem.*, 2023, **25**, 10304–10337.
- 10 H. Yue, L. Mai, C. Xu, C. Yang, P. S. Shuttleworth and Y. Cui, *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy*, 2023, **33**, 101143.
- 11 J. Luo, J. Luo, C. Yuan, W. Zhang, J. Li, Q. Gao and H. Chen, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 100849–100855.
- 12 S. Zhao, D. Kong, X. Lian, Y. Zhang, S. Xiang, F. Fu and X. Liu, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2024, **132**, 103676.
- 13 P. Solt, J. Konnerth, W. Gindl-Altmatter, W. Kantner, J. Moser, R. Mitter and H. W. G. van Herwijnen, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2019, **94**, 99–131.
- 14 M. Österberg, M. H. Sipponen, B. D. Mattos and O. J. Rojas, *Green Chem.*, 2020, **22**, 2712–2733.
- 15 A. Moreno and M. H. Sipponen, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2024, **57**, 1918–1930.
- 16 F. Wang, S. Nithianandam, I. Pylypchuk and M. H. Sipponen, *Science Advances*, 2025, **11**, eadr8372.
- 17 G. Yang, Z. Gong, X. Luo, L. Chen and L. Shuai, *Nature*, 2023, **621**, 511–515.
- 18 J. G. Lee, Y. Guo, J. A. Belgodere, A. Al Harraq, A. A. Hymel, A. J. Pete, K. T. Valsaraj, M. G. Benton, M. G. Miller, J. P. Jung and B. Bharti, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2021, **9**, 1781–1789.
- 19 T. Leskinen, J. Witos, J. J. Valle-Delgado, K. Lintinen, M. Kostianen, S. K. Wiedmer, M. Österberg and M.-L. Mattinen, *Biomacromolecules*, 2017, **18**, 2767–2776.
- 20 C. Salas, O. J. Rojas, L. A. Lucia, M. A. Hubbe and J. Genzer, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2013, **5**, 199–206.
- 21 S. Pradyawong, R. Shrestha, P. Li, X. S. Sun and D. Wang, *J Polym Environ*, 2022, **30**, 1908–1919.
- 22 Y. Yang, H. Wu, J. Zhang, T. Wen, G. Du, B. Charrier, H. Essawy, A. Pizzi, J. Wu, X. Zhou and X. Chen, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2025, **234**, 121571.
- 23 Z. Liu, T. Liu, Y. Li, X. Zhang, Y. Xu, J. Li and Q. Gao, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2022, **366**, 132906.
- 24 Y. Zhang, L. Cui, X. Che, H. Zhang, N. Shi, C. Li, Y. Chen and W. Kong, *Journal of Controlled Release*, 2015, **206**, 206–219.
- 25 S. Preetam, D. Duhita Mondal, N. Mukerjee, S. S. Naser, T. A. Tabish and N. Thorat, *ACS Biomater Sci Eng*, 2024, **10**, 1946–1965.
- 26 J. W. Lawton, *Cereal Chemistry*, 2002, **79**, 1–18.

- 27 R. Shukla and M. Cheryan, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2001, **13**, 171–192.
- 28 I. Pylypchuk and M. H. Sipponen, *Green Chem.*, 2022, **24**, 8705–8715.
- 29 P. Anastas and N. Eghbali, *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2010, **39**, 301–312.
- 30 T. Gillgren, S. A. Barker, P. S. Belton, D. M. R. Georget and M. Stading, *Biomacromolecules*, 2009, **10**, 1135–1139.
- 31 O. Faix, in *Methods in Lignin Chemistry*, eds. S. Y. Lin and C. W. Dence, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1992, pp. 83–109.
- 32 B. Wei, Y. Zhao, Y. Wei, J. Yao, X. Chen and Z. Shao, *ACS Omega*, 2019, **4**, 5609–5616.
- 33 X. Lu and X. Gu, *Biotechnol Biofuels*, 2022, **15**, 106.
- 34 J. Gendron, I. Stambouli, C. Bruel, Y. Boumghar and D. Montplaisir, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2022, **182**, 114893.
- 35 C. Sun, L. Dai, X. He, F. Liu, F. Yuan and Y. Gao, *Food Hydrocolloids*, 2016, **58**, 11–19.
- 36 Standard - Plywood - Bonding quality - Part 1, <https://www.sis.se/en/produkter/wood-technology/woodbased-panels/plywood/ssen31412005/>, (accessed March 17, 2026).
- 37 N.-E. E. Mansouri and J. Salvadó, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2006, **24**, 8–16.
- 38 R. J. Li, J. Gutierrez, Y.-L. Chung, C. W. Frank, S. L. Billington and E. S. Sattely, *Green Chem.*, 2018, **20**, 1459–1466.
- 39 I. Gavrilović-Grmuša, M. Rančić, T. Tešić, S. Stupar, M. Milošević and J. Gržetić, *Polymers*, 2024, **16**, 2602.
- 40 A. Hutchinson, Y. Liu and Y. Lu, *The Journal of Adhesion*, 2017, **93**, 737–755.
- 41 Z. Liu and F. Yan, *Advanced Science*, 2022, **9**, 2200264.
- 42 C. Bandl, W. Kern and S. Schlögl, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2020, **99**, 102585.
- 43 J. L. Thoma, R. Elsener, I. Burgert and M. Schubert, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.*, 2024, **6**, 5778–5787.
- 44 Y. Ma, Z. Kou, Y. Hu, J. Zhou, Y. Bei, L. Hu, Q. Huang, P. Jia and Y. Zhou, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2023, **126**, 103444.
- 45 N. Fantozzi, J.-N. Volle, A. Porcheddu, D. Virieux, F. García and E. Colacino, *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2023, **52**, 6680–6714.
- 46 H. Pang, C. Ma, Y. Shen, Y. Sun, J. Li, S. Zhang, L. Cai and Z. Huang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2021, **13**, 38732–38744.
- 47 S. Kong, X. Xi, H. Zhong, J. Zhu, H. Lei, X. Zhou, G. Du, A. Pizzi, H. Essawy and Q. Zhang, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2025, **13**, 20464–20475.
- 48 H. Pang, S. Zhao, Z. Wang, W. Zhang, S. Zhang and J. Li, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2020, **100**, 102600.
- 49 J. Yao, Z. Chen, C. Xu, Y. Chen, J. Guo and H. Yue, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2023, **127**, 103514.
- 50 Q. Zhang, H. Lei, G. Du, A. Pizzi, J. Song, L. Cao, B. Puangsin and X. Xi, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2024, **12**, 7903–7912.
- 51 Z. Hao, X. Xi, D. Hou, H. Lei, C. Li, G. Xu and G. Du, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 2023, **253**, 127135.
- 52 E. Cesprini, J. Jorda, M. Paolantoni, L. Valentini, P. Šket, V. Causin, D. E. Bedolla, M. Zanetti and G. Tondi, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.*, 2023, **5**, 4468–4476.
- 53 X. Zhang, Y. Zhu, Y. Yu and J. Song, *Polymers*, DOI:10.3390/polym9070261.
- 54 G. Zheng, A. Pan, Y. Xu and X. Zhang, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 2024, **213**, 118446.
- 55 D. Li, B. Zhuang, X. (Alice) Wang, Z. Wu, W. Wei, J. T. Aladejana, X. Hou, K. G. Yves, Y. Xie and J. Liu, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 2020, **277**, 123210.
- 56 X. Xi, A. Pizzi, H. Lei, B. Zhang, X. Chen and G. Du, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2022, **112**, 103027.
- 57 C. LI, H. LEI, Z. WU, X. XI, G. DU and A. Pizzi, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2022, **14**, 23859–23867.
- 58 J. Peng, F. Liu, F. Feng, X. Feng and J. Cui, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2023, **11**, 13805–13811.
- 59 C. Zuo, X.-Y. Hui, P.-A. Xin, H.-N. Qi, Z.-H. Sun, J.-L. Wen and T.-Q. Yuan, *Green Chem.*, 2026, **28**, 974–985.
- 60 Y. Zhang, M. Chen, J. Zhang, J. Li, S. Q. Shi and Q. Gao, *Advanced Materials Interfaces*, 2020, **7**, 2000148.
- 61 J. Fleming, P. Magana, S. Nair, M. Tsenkov, D. Bertoni, I. Pidruchna, M. Q. Lima Afonso, A. Midlik, U. Paramval, A. Židek, A. Laydon, O. Kovalevskiy, J. Pan, J. Cheng, Ž. Avsec, C. Bycroft, L. H. Wong, M.

- Last, M. Mirdita, M. Steinegger, P. Kohli, M. Váradi and S. Velankar, *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 2025, **437**, 168967.
- 62 J. Jumper, R. Evans, A. Pritzel, T. Green, M. Figurnov, O. Ronneberger, K. Tunyasuvunakool, R. Bates, A. Žídek, A. Potapenko, A. Bridgland, C. Meyer, S. A. A. Kohl, A. J. Ballard, A. Cowie, B. Romera-Paredes, S. Nikolov, R. Jain, J. Adler, T. Back, S. Petersen, D. Reiman, E. Clancy, M. Zielinski, M. Steinegger, M. Pacholska, T. Berghammer, S. Bodenstein, D. Silver, O. Vinyals, A. W. Senior, K. Kavukcuoglu, P. Kohli and D. Hassabis, *Nature*, 2021, **596**, 583–589.

Supplementary information

Fully bio-based wood adhesives from lignin and zein protein

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Figure S1—S7
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Figure S1. Viscosity of lignin gel and lignin-zein adhesive formulations as a function of shear rate.

a)

b)

Figure S2. Control experiments for individual adhesive components. **a)** Zein dispersed in water showing inhomogeneous aggregation and lack of processable paste formation **b)** Lignin gel only plywood sample after hot pressing, showing delamination and insufficient bonding.

Figure S3. Bonding strength for three-layer plywood cured for 15 min at 150° C. Different letters over the bars indicate significant differences between groups according to Tukey's post-hoc test following one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$). Groups sharing the same letter are not significantly different.

Figure S4. SEM images of plywood cross-section (30% lignin, 150°C, 5 min). Scale bars, from left to right: 100 μm, 50 μm (top row); 50 μm, 100 μm (middle row), 10 μm (bottom row).

Element	Line	Mass%	Atom%
C	K	42.65 ± 0.29	50.14 ± 0.11
N	K	6.82 ± 0.39	6.87 ± 0.13
O	K	45.88 ± 0.40	40.49 ± 0.11
Na	K	2.78 ± 0.05	1.71 ± 0.01
S	K	1.23 ± 0.02	0.54 ± 0.00
Cl	K	0.33 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.00
K	K	0.32 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.00
Pt	M	nd	nd
Total		100.00	100.00
Map_006_wholespectrum		Fitting ratio 0.1528	

Figure S5. EDS analysis of plywood cross-section (30% lignin formulation, 150 °C, 5 min).

Figure S6. SEM and EDS analysis of plywood cross-section (50% lignin formulation, 150 °C, 15 min). Scale bars, from left to right: 100 μm, 100 μm, 10 μm (top row); 50 μm (other images).

Table S1. Water absorption and thickness swelling of sawdust-based particleboards. Different letters over the bars indicate significant differences between groups according to Tukey's post-hoc test following one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$). Groups sharing the same letter are not significantly different.

Formulation	WA 2 h (%)	WA 6 h (%)	WA 12 h (%)	WA 24 h (%)	TS 2 h (%)	TS 6 h (%)	TS 12 h (%)	TS 24 h (%)
Adhesive 70% lignin	130.9 ± 19.3 ^a	171.5 ± 28.0 ^a	173.1 ± 26.7 ^a	153.9 ± 15.8* ^a	100.2 ± 15.5 ^a	116.5 ± 12.8 ^a	136.8 ± 9.8 ^a	144.2 ± 7.7* ^a
Adhesive 50% lignin	122.1 ± 411.8 ^a	143.7 ± 15.2 ^{ab}	156.2 ± 15.1 ^a	165.2 ± 22.0 ^a	81.1 ± 3.5 ^{ab}	97.4 ± 11.4 ^{ab}	113.1 ± 19.9 ^{ab}	121.8 ± 5.0 ^{ab}
Adhesive 30% lignin	112.2 ± 13.2 ^a	117.3 ± 11.1 ^b	136.3 ± 15.7 ^a	151.9 ± 12.9 ^a	72.5 ± 5.8 ^b	81.6 ± 3.3 ^b	90.3 ± 6.3 ^b	97.9 ± 7.5 ^b

* Partial material loss was observed for the 70% lignin formulation after 24 h immersion, which may affect the accuracy of the mass-based water absorption value.

Figure S7. Tensile strength measurement for adhesive before and after 2 reusing cycles (50% lignin formulation, 5 min curing).

Table S2. Input masses used for green metrics calculation of the lignin-zein adhesive formulation containing 50% lignin.

Component	Mass (g)	Dry content (wt%)	Dry solids (g)	Water mass (g)
Lignin gel	52.50	41	21.53	30.97
Zein	22.00	96	21.12	0.88
Added water	25.50	-	-	25.50
Total input mass	100.00	-	42.65	57.35

E-factor is defined as the mass of waste generated per mass of desired product:

$$\text{E-factor} = \text{mass of waste} / \text{mass of product} = 57.35 / 42.65 = 1.34$$

In this work, the waste mass corresponds to the total water mass in the formulation, including water present in the lignin gel, residual moisture in zein and added water used for formulation adjustment since water is evaporated during hot pressing,

Process mass intensity (PMI) is defined as the total mass used in the process required to obtain one unit mass of product:

$$\text{PMI} = \text{Total mass used in the process} / \text{mass of product} = 100 / 42.65 = 2.34$$

Process mass productivity (PMP) expresses PMI as a percentage value:

$$\text{PMP (\%)} = 1 / \text{PMI} \times 100 = 1 / 2.34 \times 100 = 42.6\%$$

Table S3. Penalty points used for Eco-scale calculations of the lignin-zein adhesive.

Parameter	Description	Penalty points
Yields	No penalty assigned	0
Price of components	No penalty assigned	0
Safety	No penalty assigned	0
Technical setup	Hot pressing / pressure equipment	3
Temperature/time	Overnight stirring during lignin gel preparation and hot pressing	3
Workup and purification	No penalty assigned	0
Total penalty points	-	6

Eco-scale was calculated by subtracting penalty points from an ideal score of 100.

Eco-scale = 100 – total penalty points = 100 – 6 = 94

Table S4. Comparison of Dry Bonding strength and bio-based content for three-layer plywood adhesives.

Material	Dry bonding strength (MPa)	Bio-based content, %	Ref
Uncondensed lignins	1.2	100	1
Lignin - glyoxal	3.9	79	2
Soy protein -acrylic acid	2	66	3
Soy protein - chitosan - CaCO ₃	2.25	77	4
Soy protein -epoxy	1.31	60	5
Cottonseed protein - Isophorone diisocyanate	2.7	85	6
Glucose - urea	1.48	83	7
Soy protein -citric acid	1.6	100	8
Tannin – furanic-silk	2.8	100	9
Soy protein - lignin-based resin	1.63	48	10
Enzymatic hydrolysis of soy protein	1.28	78	11
Chitosan - starch	2.1	95	12
Chitosan with monosaccharide	1.65	100	13
Glucose and citric acid	1.5	100	14
Tannin -polyamide	1.3	97	15
Lignin - formaldehyde	1.6	50	16
Soy bean polysaccharide -epoxy	2.1	93	17
This work	2.8	100	

Table S5. Characterization data for the lignin components used for lignin gel preparation. Data adapted from our previous work.¹⁸

Lignin type	M _w , Da	Ph-OH, mmol/g	Aliph-OH, mmol/g	COOH, mmol/g	Dispersity, Đ (M _w /M _n)	Klason Lignin (Acid insoluble lignin) %	Ref
SKL	5250	4.21	1.93	0.56	4.4	92	¹⁹
Lignosulfonate DS10	10482	0.83	3.27	0.74	5.2	96	²⁰

References:

1. Yang, G., Gong, Z., Luo, X., Chen, L. & Shuai, L. Bonding wood with uncondensed lignins as adhesives. *Nature* **621**, 511–515 (2023).
2. Siahkamari, M., Emmanuel, S., Hodge, D. B. & Nejad, M. Lignin-Glyoxal: A Fully Biobased Formaldehyde-Free Wood Adhesive for Interior Engineered Wood Products. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **10**, 3430–3441 (2022).
3. Pang, H. *et al.* Novel Bionic Soy Protein-Based Adhesive with Excellent Prepressing Adhesion, Flame Retardancy, and Mildew Resistance. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **13**, 38732–38744 (2021).
4. Kong, S. *et al.* Preparation of Soy Protein–Chitosan Adhesive Inspired by Marine Arthropod Shells with Superior Bonding Strength and Water Resistance. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **13**, 20464–20475 (2025).
5. Pang, H. *et al.* Development of soy protein-based adhesive with high water resistance and bonding strength by waterborne epoxy crosslinking strategy. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives* **100**, 102600 (2020).
6. Yao, J. *et al.* Cottonseed protein bioadhesive with high adhesion performance achieved by a synergistic dual-crosslinking strategy. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives* **127**, 103514 (2023).
7. Zhang, Q. *et al.* Easy Preparation, High Water Resistance Glucose-Based Environment-Friendly Wood Adhesives. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **12**, 7903–7912 (2024).
8. Hao, Z. *et al.* A fully bio-based soy protein wood adhesive modified by citric acid with high water tolerance. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* **253**, 127135 (2023).
9. Cesprini, E. *et al.* Bio-Based Tannin-Furanic-Silk Adhesives: Applications in Plywood and Chemical Cross-linking Mechanisms. *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* **5**, 4468–4476 (2023).
10. Zhang, X., Zhu, Y., Yu, Y. & Song, J. Improve Performance of Soy Flour-Based Adhesive with a Lignin-Based Resin. *Polymers* **9**, (2017).
11. Zheng, G., Pan, A., Xu, Y. & Zhang, X. Preparation of a superior soy protein adhesive with high solid content by enzymatic hydrolysis combined with cross-linking modification. *Industrial Crops and Products* **213**, 118446 (2024).
12. Li, D. *et al.* Chitosan used as a specific coupling agent to modify starch in preparation of adhesive film. *Journal of Cleaner Production* **277**, 123210 (2020).
13. Xi, X. *et al.* Environmentally friendly chitosan adhesives for plywood bonding. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives* **112**, 103027 (2022).
14. Li, C. *et al.* Fully Biobased Adhesive from Glucose and Citric Acid for Plywood with High Performance. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **14**, 23859–23867 (2022).
15. Peng, J., Liu, F., Feng, F., Feng, X. & Cui, J. Enhancing Environmentally Friendly Tannin Adhesive for Plywood through Hyperbranched Polyamide. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **11**, 13805–13811 (2023).
16. Zuo, C. *et al.* A green one-pot strategy for sustainable fully lignin-based adhesives. *Green Chem.* **28**, 974–985 (2026).
17. Zhang, Y. *et al.* A High-Performance Bio-Adhesive Using Hyperbranched Aminated Soybean Polysaccharide and Bio-Based Epoxide. *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **7**, 2000148 (2020).
18. Pylypchuk, I. & Sipponen, M. H. Organic solvent-free production of colloiddally stable spherical lignin nanoparticles at high mass concentrations. *Green Chem.* **24**, 8705–8715 (2022).
19. Moreno, A., Morsali, M. & Sipponen, M. H. Catalyst-Free Synthesis of Lignin Vitrimers with Tunable Mechanical Properties: Circular Polymers and Recoverable Adhesives. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **13**, 57952–57961 (2021).
20. Abbadessa, A., Oinonen, P. & Henriksson, G. Characterization of Two Novel Bio-based Materials from Pulping Process Side Streams: Ecohelix and CleanFlow Black Lignin. *BioResources* **13**, 7606–7627 (2018).